

ACRIDINE DERIVATIVES AS ANTIMALARIALS PART IV.

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Certain sulphonamidophenylsulphonamido-5-dialkylaminoalkylaminoacridines and 5-acridylsulphanilylsulphanilamides have been prepared and described. Unlike other acridine derivatives they are comparatively tasteless, but possess, particularly in neutral solutions, the characteristic fluorescence of the 5-aminoacridines.

The sulphonamido-dialkylaminoalkylaminoacridine derivatives, particularly, 3 - phenylsulphonylamido- 7 - methoxy- 5- (δ - diethylaminobutyl and ω -diethylamino-*isoamyl*)-aminoacridines, recently described by Basu and Das-Gupta in Part III* of this investigation (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 100) have since been found to possess bacteriostatic action against certain haemolytic streptococci, and also to be toxic to paramecium. It is known (*cf.* Rosenthal *et al.*, *Fub. Health Reports.*, U. S. Treas. Dept., 1937, **52**, 662 ; Fourneau *et al.*, *Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1936, **122**, 258; Whitby, *Lancet*, 1938, *ii*, 1095) that the range of activity of any sulphanilamide derivative may be considerably widened by substituting the amino hydrogen by other grouping, such as sulphonamidophenyl [*cf.* the drug, "Uleron" (I, R=Me)]. Accordingly, certain acridine derivatives of the types (II) and (III) have been synthesised and described in the experimental part of this paper. Their bacetericidal and antiparasitic actions are being studied.

* This part has been wrongly printed as Part II.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

2-Chloro-5-sulphonyl-(p'-sulphonamidophenyl)-aminobenzoic Acid.—1 Mol. of 1-carboxy-2-chlorobenzene-5-sulphonyl chloride (Basu and Das-Gupta, *loc. cit.*) and 2 mols. of *p*-aminobenzenesulphonamide were rubbed together with a little water in a mortar for about 2 hours and sodium carbonate was added to the mixture to keep it alkaline and the mixture left overnight. It was then filtered and the filtrate acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid in the cold. The acid separated in a semi-solid state which after some time set to a crystalline mass. This was collected, washed and crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 240°. (Found: N, 7.08. $C_{13}H_{11}O_6N_2ClS_2$ requires N, 7.17 per cent).

4-Sulphonyl-(p'-sulphonamidophenyl)-amino-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic Acid.—2-Chloro-5-sulphonyl-(*p'*-sulphonamidophenyl)-amino-benzoic acid (15.6 g.), *p*-anisidine (5 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (5.5 g.) were refluxed together in amyl alcoholic solution with little copper powder for about 4 hours. The mixture was diluted with a little water and distilled in steam. The residue was then filtered and the filtrate acidified in the cold with dilute hydrochloric acid. The acid, thus obtained, was crystallised from dilute alcohol (charcoal) in almost colourless needles, m.p. 246°. (Found: N, 8.45. $C_{20}H_{19}O_7N_3S_2$ requires N, 8.8 per cent).

3-Sulphonyl-(p'-sulphonamidophenyl)-amino-7-methoxy-5-chloroacridine.—4-Sulphonyl-(*p'*-sulphonamidophenyl)-amino-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid was heated with excess of phosphorus oxychloride on a boiling water-bath for more than 2 hours and then the oxychloride was removed in *vacuo*. The residual mass was decomposed with ice-cold water and made just alkaline with ammonia. The solid obtained was crystallised from a mixture of acetone and water (charcoal) in brownish yellow needles, m.p. 212-15°. The compound is soluble in dilute alkalis and acids and is slightly fluorescent in alcoholic solution. (Found: N, 8.82; Cl, 7.28. $C_{20}H_{16}O_5N_3ClS_2$ requires N, 8.79; Cl, 7.43 per cent).

3-Sulphonyl-(p'-sulphonamidophenyl)-amino-7-methoxy-5-(ω -diethyl-aminoisoamyl)-aminocridine (structure analogous to II).—To a solution of 3-sulphonyl-(*p'*-sulphonamidophenyl)-amino-7-methoxy-5-chloroacridine (3 g.) dissolved in phenol (10 g.) at 100° δ -diethylamino- α -methylbutylamine (2 g.) was added slowly and the solution kept at 100° for 2 hours. It was then poured into about 150 c.c. of 5% sodium hydroxide solution in the cold. The alkaline solution was extracted several times with ether and made almost neutral by adding hydrochloric acid when a semi-solid mass separated. It was collected, washed with ice-cold water and dissolved in glacial acetic acid

and filtered. The acetic acid solution was extracted several times with ether and made strongly alkaline with ammonia in the cold, and left overnight. The precipitate obtained was washed, dried and crystallised from acetone-petroleum ether mixture (1 : 4) in yellow crystals, m.p. 254-56°. (Found: N, 11.82; S, 10.9. $C_{29}H_{37}O_5N_5S_2$ requires N, 11.69; S, 10.68 per cent). The compound is tasteless and soluble in acids and alkalis. It gives high fluorescence (emerald green) in alcoholic solution; the acid and alkali solutions give weaker fluorescence, showing that it exists in acridonimine form (Basu and Das-Gupta, *loc. cit.*).

3-Sulphonyl-(*p'*-sulphonamidophenyl)-amino-7-methoxy-5-(δ -diethylaminobutyl)-aminoacridine (structure analogous to II).—3-Sulphonyl-(*p'*-sulphonamidophenyl)-amino-7-methoxy-5-chloroacridine (3 g.) dissolved in phenol (10 g) at 100° was condensed with δ -diethylaminobutylamine (2 g.) for 2 hours. The acridine derivative was isolated as in the foregoing compound and crystallised from acetone-petroleum ether mixture in yellow crystals, m.p. 220-22°. Its properties are similar to the previous compound. (Found: N, 11.65; $C_{28}H_{35}O_5N_5S_2$ requires N, 11.96 per cent).

2-Chloro-5-sulphonyl-(*p'*-sulphondiethylamidophenyl)-aminobenzoic Acid.—*p*-Aminobenzenesulphon-diethylamide (2 mol.) and 1-carboxy-2-chlorobenzene-5-sulphonyl chloride (1 mol.) were reacted in the manner as in the previous case. The acid, isolated as a semi-solid mass, set to crystalline solid on treatment with ether. It separated from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 194-95°. (Found: N, 6.15. $C_{17}H_{19}O_6N_2ClS_2$ requires N, 6.27 per cent).

4-Sulphon-(*p'*-sulphondiethylamidophenyl)-amino-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic Acid.—2-Chloro-5-sulphonyl-(*p'*-sulphondiethylamidophenyl)-aminobenzoic acid and *p*-anisidine were condensed in amyl alcoholic solution with a little copper powder and anhydrous potassium carbonate for 4 hours. After usual treatment, the diphenylamine acid was crystallised from dilute alcohol (charcoal) in almost colourless needles, m. p. 202-3°. (Found: N, 7.67. $C_{24}H_{27}O_7N_3S_2$ requires N, 7.88 per cent).

3-Sulphonyl-(*p'*-sulphondiethylamidophenyl)-amino-7-methoxy-5-chloroacridine. — 4-Sulphon-(*p'*-sulphondiethylamidophenyl)-amino-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid was acridinated with phosphorus oxychloride at 100° on a water-bath for 2 hours. The chloroacridine was isolated as usual and crystallised from acetone in yellow needles, m.p. 187-89°. It gave weak fluorescence in alcoholic solution. (Found: N, 7.92; Cl, 6.42. $C_{24}H_{24}O_5N_3ClS_2$ requires N, 7.87; Cl, 6.65 per cent).

3-Sulphonyl-(*p*-sulphondiethylamidophenyl)-amino-7-methoxy-5-(ω -diethylaminoisomyl)-aminoacridine.—The above chloroacridine (3 g.)

dissolved in phenol (10 g.) was condensed with δ -diethylamino- α -methylbutylamine (1.6 g.) by heating for 1½ hours. The acridine derivative was finally crystallised in orange-yellow crystals from a mixture of acetone and petroleum ether melting indefinitely at 160°. It is almost tasteless but possesses all the other usual characteristics. (Found : N, 10.65; S, 10.04. $C_{33}H_{45}O_5N_3S_2$ requires N, 10.69; S, 9.77 per cent).

3-Sulphonyl-(p'-sulphondiethylaminophenyl)-amino-7-methoxy-5-(δ -diethylaminobutyl)-aminoacridine.—This was prepared from the corresponding 5-chloroacridine (3 g.) and δ -diethylaminobutylamine (1.5 g.) in the usual way, and was finally obtained in orange-yellow crystals from acetone-petroleum ether, m.p. 130° (indefinite). Its properties are similar to its analogues described. (Found : N, 10.61; S, 9.84. $C_{32}H_{43}O_5N_3S_2$ requires N, 10.91; S, 9.98 per cent).

3-Sulphonyl-(p'-sulphondiethylamidophenyl)-amino-7-methoxy-5-(γ -diethylaminopropyl)-aminoacridine.—This was obtained from the chloroacridine (3 g.) and γ -diethylaminopropylamine (1.4 g.) After isolation in the usual way it crystallised from acetone-petroleum ether in yellow crystals, m.p. 200° (indefinite). (Found : N, 11.27. $C_{31}H_{41}O_5N_3S_2$ requires N, 11.16 per cent).

p-Aminobenzenesulphonylaminobenzene-4-sulphondiethylamide (I, R = Et).—*p*-Aminobenzene-sulphondiethylamide (1 mol.) and *p*-acetylaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride (1 mol.) were rubbed with a little water in a mortar for several hours and left overnight. Sodium carbonate was added occasionally to keep the mixture alkaline. The solid obtained after filtration was extracted with hot benzene. The residue (acetyl derivative) was crystallised from alcohol in colourless crystals, m.p. 228°. (Found : N, 10.03. $C_{18}H_{23}O_5N_3S_2$ requires N, 9.88 per cent).

The acetyl derivative was hydrolysed by refluxing with a little excess of 5% aqueous-alcoholic hydrochloric acid for ½ hour till a clear solution resulted. This was then made just alkaline with dilute ammonia in the cold. The precipitated solids were collected and crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless crystals, m.p. 176°. (Found : N, 11.14. $C_{16}H_{21}O_4N_3S_2$ requires N, 10.96 per cent).

Formation of (III, R = Et).—Equimolecular quantities of 2-chloro-7-methoxy-5-chloroacridine and (I, R = Et) were heated in phenol at 140° for about 3 hours. The mixture was then poured into dilute caustic soda solution in the cold. The separated solids were collected and treated with dilute acetic acid and filtered. The residue was dried and crystallised from acetone-petroleum ether mixture (1 : 4) in bright yellow crystals, m.p. 160-61°. It

gives weak fluorescence in alcoholic solution. (Found : N, 8.66 ; S, 10.14. $C_{30}H_{29}O_5N_4ClS_2$ requires N, 8.96 ; S, 10.24 per cent).

Formation of (III, R=Et and Me in place of methoxyl).—This was obtained from 2-chloro-7-methyl-5-chloroacridine and I (R=Et) as previously described. It was crystallised from acetone-petroleum ether in yellow crystals, m.p. 133-34°. (Found : N, 9.05. $C_{30}H_{29}O_4N_4ClS_2$ requires N, 9.2 per cent).

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